

The Relationship between Performance Standards and Achieving the Objectives of Supervision at the Islamic University in Gaza

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Abstract: *The aim of the research is to identify the relationship between the performance criteria and the achievement of the objectives of supervision which is represented in the performance of the job at the Islamic University in Gaza Strip. To achieve the objectives of the research, the researchers used the descriptive analytical approach to collect information. The questionnaire consisted of (22) paragraphs distributed to three categories of employees of the Islamic University (senior management, faculty members, their assistants and members of the administrative board). A random sample of 314 employees was selected, 276 responses were retrieved with a return rate of 88.1%. The SPSS program was used to enter, process, and analyze the data. The results of the study showed a positive relationship between the performance criteria and the achievement of the control objectives represented by the job performance in the Islamic University from the point of view of the members (senior management, faculty and their assistants and the administrative board).*

The researchers also recommended a number of recommendations, including the provision of an appropriate level of control system components today through the continuous updating and development of performance standards and the need to provide the necessary physical and financial resources to continue the development and achievement within the university. Expand the development of technology in the various activities of the university through the construction of a complete and integrated system to support the control systems in the university to suit its size. The researchers also recommended the follow-up, review of the performance standards and work to modify them in line with the mission of the university and the goals that the university seeks to reach.

Keywords: Performance Standards, Supervision, Palestinian Universities, Islamic University, Gaza, Palestine.

1. INTRODUCTION

The issue of control is both original and modern. It is authentic because control is essential in any organization and is one of the basic elements of the administrative process of planning, organizing, directing and controlling. In addition, it is a modern subject because of its recent trends that were not known before. Control is applied in all areas of activity. As a permanent function and is defined as an administrative activity that verifies that what has been implemented or carried out is the same as planned.

It has been agreed by the scholars of management and modern administrators that the achievement of control is linked to the degree of coordination between the administrative processes practiced in those organizations, and they see that the interaction of the elements of the administrative process is the real indicator of the success of any administrative work, and perhaps the most prominent of these elements is the control that seeks to unite financial and human resources and channeling their efforts to the right track (Alaqati, 2000).

The process of measurement and performance evaluation is a step in the series of the regulatory system in the organization. This process is difficult and facilitated by the accuracy of specific criteria that are not likely to be tried or evaluated. The more the criteria are clear and specific, the easier the measurement is, the faster and clearer the purpose of the regulatory system in any organization is to ensure that the actual performance of the planned performance is matched and to take the necessary action to correct the deviations shown by the evaluation and measurement.

The goal of any regulatory system is to raise the level of the employees' performance and to invest their abilities and potentials in order to help them progress by recognizing how they perform scientifically and objectively (Jad Al-rab, 2009).

The Palestinian universities, including the Islamic University, are considered one of the most important pillars of social and economic development. They play an important role in the development of human and material resources in Palestine. They need to have a system of performance evaluation based on specific criteria. The components of the university work that can be measured so that through these standards can judge the performance of the university and its employees and the extent of their ability to promote the mission of the university defined in its basic goals.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

In the light of the exploratory study conducted by the researchers, the researcher found that the research problem can be formulated as follows:

Q1- Is there a relationship between the performance standards and the level of performance of the employees at the Islamic University? What is the degree and quality of this relationship?

3. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

This study aims to achieve a number of objectives, the most important of which are the following:

1. To clarify the important role played by the supervision systems at the Islamic University in the Gaza Strip and to verify the strength or weakness of the university.
2. Identify the availability of the elements of the control systems at the Islamic University in the Gaza Strip.
3. A statement of the relationship between the performance standards and the achievement of the objectives of the Islamic University supervision in the Gaza Strip.

4. RESEARCH IMPORTANCE

The importance of research is summarized in the following points:

1. This study is one of the studies that have focused on the subject of performance control in educational institutions.
2. This study can be used to identify methods, programs and methods by which the process can be properly monitored at the university.
3. This research may positively influence senior management (decision makers) by providing them with information about the reality of the control systems at the Islamic University in the Gaza Strip.
4. This study may represent a picture of the evaluation of the performance control systems, whose results and recommendations may be of importance to those interested in this subject and constitute the scientific beginning on the way to help the Islamic University in the field of performance control.

5. RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

H01: There is a significant relationship between the performance criteria and the performance of the job at the Islamic University in Gaza Strip.

6. RESEARCH LIMITS AND SCOPE

1. **Subject Limit (Academic):** The objective of the study was to study the relationship between performance standards and achieve the objectives of supervision at the Islamic University of Gaza
2. **Human Limit:** The study was conducted on all employees (senior management, faculty members, their assistants and members of the administrative board) at the Islamic University under study.
3. **Institutional limitation:** The study was conducted on Palestinian universities.
4. **The spatial limit:** The study was conducted in the State of Palestine, and was limited to the Islamic University.
5. **Time Limits:** The study was conducted in 2017.

7. LITERATURE REVIEW

- Study of (Saleem, Irfan et.al. 2014) aimed at identifying the most important HR practices that affect job performance. And to study the relationship between the organizational commitment and the enhancement of the performance of the employees. And study the relationship between transparency, testing, recruitment and job performance. And study the relationship between the development and functional performance of employees.

The results showed that there is a positive effect between regulatory compliance and job performance enhancement. It also found a strong correlation between transparency in hiring and selecting employees and enhancing their job performance. Furthermore, there is a strong relationship between development programs and enhancing the performance of employees.

- A study of (Kazan, 2013) aimed at studying and measuring the performance of employees in the service sector in the performance of government banks in Turkey. Identify the most important factors affecting the performance of workers in the service sector in public banks. The results showed that there is a positive impact of the sense of belonging to the performance of employees in banks. The physical and moral environment has a positive impact on the performance of bank employees. The results showed that there is a positive effect for salaries, grants for employees, level of job satisfaction, promotion systems, career advancement, employment relations and incentives for job performance.
- The study of (Olorunsola E.O, 2012) aimed at identifying the level of performance of administrative staff in the Nigerian universities in Western Nigeria in the south from the perspective of managers and departments. Study the impact of sex factor on the performance and functions of administrators. The most important results were that the performance of the employees of these universities was very high for all factors related to performance. The results showed that the increase in the performance of workers may be due to the quality and the ability demonstrated by the leadership in dealing with others. She emphasized that there were no significant differences in the job performance due to the gender factor. Performance was high among males and females from these universities.
- A study of (Madi, 2011) aimed at studying the degree of application of the major municipalities to the role of knowledge management in the performance of the function from the point of view of managers. The most important findings were that there were positive trends but not the level required for the role of knowledge management in the performance of the job. A favorable relationship between knowledge at the functional level.
- Study of (Ben Tarif, 2010) which aimed to identify the impact of control units in the effectiveness of Jordanian ministries from the point of view of their employees. The most important results were the existence of a statistically significant effect on the combined control dimensions (adequacy of legislations, efficiency of human resources, objectives of administrative control, supervision competencies, and technology used) and effectiveness of Jordanian ministries.
- Study of (Hawk, 2010) which aimed at determining whether there were significant differences in the performance ratings of the general staff working in the administrative and financial services department of the university mentioned above who participated in the informal monitoring programs with the control group, which do not have informal monitors as contained in the self-reports in the survey. The main findings were that there were no differences in the overall score of performance evaluation among employees who participated in informal monitoring compared with those who participated in informal monitoring with the informal control group. There was no relationship between the length of time of the informal monitoring relationship and performance ratings. And the importance of informal monitoring as a tool for professional development to attract and anticipate employees.
- Study of (Botora, 2007) aims at clarifying the effectiveness of the system of internal control in banks, and through a case study of one of the Algerian banks, which reached the results of the most important that the control system is an imperative in all financial institutions. Proper design of the control system would support the objectives of the system. Proper administrative procedures for monitoring positively affect the support of regulatory objectives. Developments in internal control systems through the introduction of a new organizational structure augur well-suited applications, as supporting the organization with a larger number of staff helps to accomplish work more efficiently than if multiple tasks are assigned to one person.
- Study of (Shaheen, 2007) which aimed to identify administrative control and its important role in achieving the objectives of NGOs. And to identify some of the factors affecting internal control. The most important results were the existence of a positive relationship between the internal controls and the achievement of its objectives. Internal control systems applied by NGOs in the Gaza Strip achieve their objectives. And that there is a strong relationship between the availability of organizational structure and the achievement of regulatory objectives to contribute to the achievement of the objectives of NGOs, including the performance of associations.
- Study of (Jaclyne, 2006) aimed at identifying the central control systems in control and prevents deviations occurring in the organization. The most important findings were that censorship plays a major role in controlling behavior and improving employee performance. Oversight plays a major role in the commitment of employees to the standards of work and their performance and their needs. Control plays a major role in preventing deviations in performance and solving problems that occur at work.

- Study of (Bierstaker, 2005) which aimed to examine the relationship between the internal control systems in some public sector institutions in Sweden and the quality of the employees' performance. The most important results were that there is a positive impact of the quality control systems on performance in terms of speed and accuracy. There is a positive relationship and statistical significance between the control systems and performance due to the personal and functional variables of the sample of the study.

8. THE THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

First- Control

▪ Control concept:

Control is applied in all areas of human activity. It is a permanent function and a continuous self-operation that should be carried out in terms of a system of performance control and ensuring the achievement of the objectives set forth in the plans. Supervision is an important pillar of modern management and occupies an important position between planning, organization and guidance (Al-Sawafiri and others, 2002).

Supervision is defined as that part of the Director's job, which is concerned with the review of the various tasks related to reviewing the various tasks and verifying what has been implemented and comparing it with what must be implemented and necessary in the case of the different course of the two (Franklin, 1964). Thus, the general concept of supervision as an administrative function involves carrying out all the necessary activities and procedures at any level to ascertain the objectives achieved according to the desired levels. The deviations are then identified and the process of dealing with them begins. Therefore, censorship is one of the main administrative functions by which the extent to which the objectives are achieved can be ascertained.

▪ Characteristics of good control system:

Triotha and Newort designated six characteristics of a good control system regardless of how different the control system, the organization, and its activity. There are general characteristics that must be taken into account by the manager at each level of management control that can be summarized below (H.Koontz & Cyrit, 1976).

1. Speed of detecting the deviations: In order to be effective control system, deviations must be reported in a timely manner, so that appropriate corrective action can be taken before things are out of control.
2. Relevance: It is necessary for the control system to conform to the nature of the organization's activity, size, objectives, future aspirations and the type of industry to which it belongs. A large, complex enterprise requires a complex and comprehensive control system, while a small and limited enterprise need simplified control system.
3. Flexibility: It is intended to respond to changes, as the characteristic of the business environment today is dynamic and continuous change, so the control system must be flexible and adaptable. Otherwise it will be unable to cope with adaptive changes, adaptive changes and adaptations to conditions of work or implementation.
4. Clarity and ease of understanding: to achieve this must be commensurate with the competencies in the organization, that is not only the existence of the system, but the possibility of application and success, and must include control standards and easy to modify if necessary. Control methods must be straightforward and understandable by the control bodies.
5. Economic: It is assumed that the use of control systems commensurate with the potential of the organization, and the objectives to be achieved. Thus, the cost of an effective control system must be less than the return earned by that system.
6. Integration: Integration of control systems indicates that these systems need to be assimilated to all standards of all organizational plans, and that the same schemes must be integrated with the control systems used.

▪ Types of control:

Monitoring can be divided into several types according to a number of different criteria (Al-saeed, 2013):

1. Control in terms of time (before, during and after implementation)
2. Control in terms of source (internal and external)
3. Supervision by level: (strategy - structural - financial - operations)
4. Supervision by specialization or activity

Performance criteria in the audit process:

There are three stages or steps in which the control process goes through. Regardless of the activity under control: setting performance standards, measuring performance and correcting deviations. Here we will discuss performance standards and their relationship to functional performance as part of the regulatory system.

The criteria are specific patterns or levels of performance to be achieved through implementation. These criteria measure and evaluate performance and the plan is the basis of control. Therefore, the objectives of the plan are considered as desirable performance criteria.

The criteria include two types of descriptive standards, which are difficult and complex in nature, and these criteria are often to evaluate the efficiency and adequacy of services provided by service organizations.

The other criteria are quantitative criteria, which are easy to determine, control and control, such as the specific sales volume, the total profit, the cost of capital. These standards are used in the productive activity.

Standards must be comprehensive to serve all activities at different levels. There are standards at the organization level that define their basic objectives and standards at the level of executive departments such as production, marketing, procurement and warehouse management, and there are other standards at the individual level which measure labor efficiency and quality.

The establishment of precise and clear criteria for measuring and evaluating the quality of educational services for the college or university is done through the reality of the labor market and from the experience of the educational institution in the field of university education. To succeed in this, there is a need to develop indicators and measures capable of achieving the evaluation of the quality of educational services. These standards are essential to the success of the performance appraisal process, as they help to define what employees are required to achieve the organization's objectives and to guide managers to what needs to be taken into account to improve performance.

▪ **Types of performance standards**

There are two types of performance evaluation criteria:

Element criteria and performance rate criteria are (Al-Hiti, 2003).

1. **Performance Standards:** They can be defined as a balance by which the resident can weigh employee productivity to see how well it is in terms of quality and quantity over a specified period of time. This is done by comparing the work done to the employee to the specified rate, in order to finally determine the level of production in terms of quantity or quality. Performance rates have three types:
 - A. **Quantitative rates:** A certain quantity of production units that must be produced within a specified time period is determined.
 - B. **Specific rates:** means that the production of the individual must reach a level of quality, accuracy and proficiency.
 - C. **Quantitative and qualitative averages:** This rate is a combination of the two previous types, whereby the production of the individual must reach a certain number of units within a specified time period. At a certain level of quality and mastery.

The standard, however important, must be precise in the expression of the performance to be measured and should be characterized by the following characteristics:

2. **The meter is valid:** the factors included in the scale must reflect those characteristics required by the performance of the work without increasing or decreasing, and there are two cases in which the scale is not true. Namely:
 - If the scale does not contain key performance factors, this type of error is known as the scale failure.
 - In the case that it contains effects beyond the will of the individual, and this type of error known as pollution of the scale.
3. **Stability of the scale:** means that the results of an individual's work through the scale are constant when the performance is constant, but when the results of the measurement vary with different degrees or levels of performance. This is not a defect but a natural state.
4. **Discipline:** The degree of sensitivity of a measure is to show differences in performance levels, however simple, distinguishing between the performance of an individual or a group of individuals.
5. **Ease of use of the meter:** We mean the clarity of the scale and its use by subordinates at work.
6. **Acceptance:** means the standard that refers to justice. And reflects the actual performance of individuals (Naguib, 2005).

Many studies have shown the importance of auditing standards in any organization, regardless of the nature of their work, including Madi (2011). The weakness in the use of performance standards in the control process has a negative impact on the effectiveness of the organization. Performance criteria are used objectively and positively

affect the performance of staff in the organization and that the standards are developed by the higher supervisors, which positively affect performance.

Poon (2003) study showed that bias and manipulation in the use of performance criteria influenced job performance assessment, job dissatisfaction and the desire to quit. Bierstaker (2004) showed that control systems, including performance standards, affect the quality of performance in terms of speed and accuracy.

Second- the performance

Performance concept:

Performance occupies a special place within any organization, both private and public, as the ultimate outcome of all activities at the level of the individual, organization or state, because the organization is more stable and longer lasting when the performance of its employees is distinct (Durrah, 2003). Performance is defined as an interaction of an employee's behavior, and that behavior is determined and its effort and ability interact. It is also known as the interaction between behavior and achievement or the total behavior and results achieved together with the tendency to highlight achievement or results because of the difficulty of separating behavior on the one hand and achievement and outcomes in the other (Al-Joueidi, 2007). The performance of the employees plays an important role in determining and measuring the performance of the organization. Individuals and high performers have the ability to help the organization achieve its strategic objectives, thus achieving the competitive advantage of the organization and maintaining it (Al-Fayedi, 2008).

Job performance occupies a special place within any civil society organization, considering the final outcome of all activities. At the level of the individual, the organization and the State, because the Organization is more stable and longer-lasting, with a distinct performance of its personnel (Tomaka, 2001).

Performance types:

Performance classification and type selection require the choice of the exact and scientific criterion that can be relied upon to determine the different types and criteria on which to classify performance (Steven.et al, 2009):

- Standard of Inclusiveness:

According to the criteria of inclusiveness, which divide the objectives into total and partial, the performance can be divided into:

Overall Performance: This is reflected in the achievements that all elements, functions and subsystems of the Organization contributed to it. It cannot be proportionate to any element without the contribution of the rest of the elements, and within this type of performance can talk about the extent and how to achieve the Organization's overall objectives such as continuity, profits, growth and other goals.

Partial performance is achieved at the level of the organization's sub-systems and is in turn divided into several types according to the different criteria to evaluate the organized elements. It is divided into several types according to the different criteria used to evaluate the organization's components. The overall performance of the organization is the result of the interplay performance of its various subsystems.

- Standard Term:

Performance according to this criterion is divided into long, medium and short term. This type of classification is difficult to implement and cannot be relied upon accurately. This is because of the difficulty of separating the term and setting its date in advance to approximate.

- Standard Nature:

Performance is categorized according to nature, economic, social, political, and technical, as the organization cannot achieve economic performance without a technological presence (Abdul Samad, 2008).

Institutional performance: In order for the organization to continue, it must function well and use resources effectively to serve the consumers. The concept of value creation is very important in the context of the organization's continuity equation and the ability of organized processes to add value far exceeds the costs of using resources as inputs gives the organization outstanding performance and high productivity(Al-Amiri and Alghalebi, 2008).

The overall performance of the organization can be measured by three important indicators addressed by business literature (Shujun, 2007):

1. Effectiveness: It is the measurement of the extent to which the organization's objectives are achieved.
2. Efficiency: It is a measure of the extent to which resources that are linked to specific objectives are used.
3. Productivity: It is the relationship between the quantity and type of performance and the exploitation of resources.

Indicators for measuring and evaluating performance in educational institutions:

There is a set of indicators to assess university performance as this evaluation process is a complex matter especially considering that universities provide research, scientific and advisory services. There are a number of indicators used to measure and evaluate the effectiveness of university performance.

A. Indicators of educational activity evaluation: This is done through the following:

1. Percentage of faculty members to students (Jad Al-rab, 2009).
2. Percentage of faculty members / researchers.
3. The proportion of assigned staff members to the appointees: the more this percentage the lower the efficiency of the educational and research process.
4. The structural distribution of faculty members by degree: The more the number of professors the better, the following ratios must be known:
 - Percentage of professors to total faculty members.
 - Percentage of teachers to total faculty members.
5. Number and percentage of those who did not graduate from the faculty members on their dates.
6. Ratio of loaned / total faculty members: the higher this percentage, the local university system is considered an oppressor of the most important categories.
7. Percentage of holders of degrees from foreign countries / total faculty members who have the same grades.
8. Number and percentage of those returning after the end of their missions.
9. Percentage of faculty members / support groups.
10. Percentage of scientific research in the Department / College / University / State.
11. The quality of educational curricula in terms of (modernity, originality and development), keeping abreast of the curricula of local and international environmental conditions, presentation of curricula to local and international environmental conditions, and presentation of curricula through various media such as books, memos, internet, e-books, university libraries. Data and information. The method of presentation of the curriculum and follow-up and the series of ideas in it. The clarity of the objective and the message of the content of the courses printed or displayed electronically.
12. Methods of case study, method of case study, method of case study, method of representation of roles, method of research project, simulation method, electronic methods in the presentation of curricula through the use of computer technology e.
13. The number of hours spent by the student in theoretical studies of the course, compared to the number of practical or practical hours.
14. The number of hours of study in the classrooms and the grades / number of hours spent by the student in the practical training in one of the community institutions related to his specialization.
15. efficiency and quality of the laboratory through: (capacity of the laboratory for the number of students and the adequacy of laboratory capabilities, the efficiency and of equipment and operating requirements, safety degrees and protect the health of students from the damage of pollution and radiation,
16. Efficiency of supervision and follow-up study through the presence of an integrated working team continues:
 - Advertising schedules and exams in appropriate places
 - Follow-up of the commitment of faculty members and their assistants to attend lectures at specified times.
 - And other supervision and follow-up processes.
17. The efficiency of the assessment process of university students examinations through the efficiency of the systems of examinations in force, how to distribute the total score of the course on the number of examinations that are, the adequacy of the time allocated for examinations and others.
18. The efficiency of the library through the quality of the books and the sources of knowledge, quality and novelty and relevance to the study concerned and the capacity and efficiency of the process of furnishing the library and the efficiency of the space allocated for the view.

B. Evaluation of Post Graduate Activities:

This is done through several indicators:

The adequacy and efficiency of faculty members and the number of professors, assistants, teachers, assistant and teachers. The proportion of each category to the other groups. The efficiency of the organizational and human structures in the field of postgraduate studies in the university. The percentage of expenditure on scientific research and graduate studies at the national level and at the level of each research institution. The number of researchers obtaining degrees from abroad. The number of distinguished scientists and researchers at the level in their fields of specialization. And the extent of the efficiency of the resources and the material, laboratory and research potential to carry out scientific and innovative research and the number of research or researchers who have received certificates of appreciation or rewards distinguished at the international or local level.

C. Assessing the Performance of the Community Service and Environmental Development Sector (Abu El-Nasr, 2008):

This is done by measuring the following indicators:

The senior management of the universities is convinced of the strategic importance of this sector, and this is evidenced by: Appointing distinguished scientific and administrative competencies, the provision of budgets for expenditure, strong organizational, managerial structures and clear objectives, moral support through meetings, seminars and national celebrations, whether environmental, cultural, political or social and others.

D. Evaluation of the efficiency of administrative and financial systems:

The administrative and financial system is the driving force of the university's education, research and studies systems, and unless it is effective and efficient, the university system will be exposed to multiple risks that may lead to its failure to achieve its mission.

E. Quantitative Evaluation of University Performance:

It is possible to use the following indicators, some of which were mentioned during the advanced presentation and other indicators, the most important of which are: (the rates of turnover, staff turnover rates, absenteeism, delay and absenteeism rates, success rate at the university level as a whole, the proportion of cases of dismissal / total cases of students, the success rate and the degree of excellent or very good.

The evaluation of university performance is not an end in itself, but rather a means by which to identify and improve strengths and excellence, to identify and remedy weaknesses and shortcomings, to ensure that they are not replicated, to develop plans for development, change and restructuring within academic institutions so as to advance their academic and applied National or global level. The following figure (1) illustrates the integration of subsystems to assess the overall performance of scientific and university institutions.

Figure 1: Clarification of the integration of subsystems to evaluate the overall performance of scientific and university institutions

Source: Jad Al-rab, Saied (2009). Strategies for Developing and Improving Performance, Methodological Frameworks and Practical Applications, Cairo, Dar Al Fajr Publishing and Distribution Library, p. 522.

9. STUDY PROCEDURES

The research problem can be formulated as follows:

Is there a relationship between the performance standards and the level of performance of the employees at the Islamic University? What is the degree and quality of this relationship?

Accordingly, the main hypothesis of the research is as follows:

There is a significant correlation between performance criteria and job performance at the Islamic University in the Gaza Strip.

The community of the study consists of all employees (academic, administrative) in the Islamic University (1700 employees and employees).

The researchers used the random stratified sample method by the University for the Three Categories of study (senior management, faculty members, their assistants and members of the administrative board). A survey sample (30) was distributed to the employees to test the internal consistency, structural and stability of the questionnaire. After verifying the reliability of the test, (314) questionnaires were distributed on the employees (senior management, faculty members and their assistants, members of the administrative board) and (276) were retrieved, with recovery rate (88.1%).

Table (1) shows the distribution of the study sample as follows:

Table 1: Distribution of the sample of the study

Organization	The ratio	The number
Senior management	%12.8	40
members of the Administrative board	%47.8	150
Faculty members and their assistants	%39.4	124
Total	%100	314

Source: researchers' preparation

The researchers adopted the survey list as a key tool for collecting primary data needed to achieve research objectives, measuring its variables and testing its questions and hypotheses. They were divided into two axes:

* The first dimension: discusses (performance standards) and consists of (10) paragraphs.

* Second dimension: Discusses (functional performance) and consists of (12) paragraphs.

Reliability and consistency of the questionnaire:

The paragraphs of the questionnaire were standardized in order to ascertain the veracity and consistency of their paragraphs as follows:

- **Validate the paragraphs of the questionnaire:**

The veracity of the questionnaire was confirmed in two ways:

1. The apparent honesty of the tool (sincerity of the arbitrators):

The researchers presented the questionnaire to a group of faculty members, administrative and statisticians. The researchers responded to the opinions of the arbitrators and made the necessary deletion and modification in the light of their proposals after registering them in a form prepared for this purpose.

2. Sincerity measurement:

A. Internal consistency of resolution paragraphs:

By calculating Pearson correlation coefficients between each paragraph and the total score of its axis, as follows:

B. Internal validity of the components of performance control systems:

First: the internal validity of the paragraphs of the axis of performance standards

The correlation coefficients between each of the axes of the axis "performance criteria" and the overall rate of its verbs are at the level of significance (0.05).

Second: Internal validity of the paragraphs of the axis of functional performance:

The correlation coefficients between each of the paragraphs of the axis, "functional performance" and the overall rate of its vertebrates, which shows that the correlation coefficients shown at the level of significance (0.05)

C. Reliability of structural consistency between the dimensions of the questionnaire:

Table (2) shows the correlation coefficients between the mean of each axis of the research with the total rate of the questionnaire paragraphs, which shows that the correlation coefficients shown at the level of significance (0.05), where the level of significance for each paragraph less than (0.05) and the value of calculated (r) is greater than the tabular (r) which equal to (0.361).

Table 2: The coefficient of correlation between the rate of each axis of the research with the total rate of the resolution paragraphs

The hub	Coefficient of correlation	Level of significance
Performance Standards	0.668	0.000
Functionality	0.769	0.000

D. Reliability of the search tool verbs Reliability:

– **Cronbach's Alpha Method:**

The Alpha-Cronbach method was used to measure questionnaire stability as a second method of measuring stability. Table (3) shows that stability coefficients are high.

Table 3: Stability coefficient (Alpha Cronbach method)

The hub	Number of paragraphs	Alpha Cronbach coefficient
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Performance Standards	10	0.911
Functionality	12	0.8975
All paragraphs	22	0.8908

We conclude from the results of the tests of truthfulness and stability that the research tool (the questionnaire) is honest in measuring what has been set for measurement, and it is very stable at a very high level, which qualifies it to be an appropriate and effective measurement tool for this research and can be applied with confidence.

Test the imposition of research:

One sample T test was used to answer the study questions, and the paragraph is positive, meaning that the respondents agree with their content if the calculated t value is greater than the tabular t value(1.97) (or the probability value less than 0.05 and the weight is greater than 60%). The percentage is negative in the sense that the sample does not agree with its content if the calculated t value is smaller than the tabular t value(-1.97) (or the probability value is less than 0.05 and the relative weight is less than 60%). The sample in the paragraph is neutral if the probability value is greater than (0.05).

Analysis of Performance Standards

The t-test was used for a single sample, and the results are shown in Table (4) which shows the views of the sample of the study sample in the paragraphs of the "performance criteria" axis.

Table 4: Analysis of the paragraphs of "Performance Standards"

Organization	Arithmetic mean	Relative weight	standard deviation	T value	Probability Value
Senior management	3.86	77.58	0.931	5.52	0.000
Faculty members and their assistants	3.46	74.76	0.921	6.79	
Members of the administrative board	3.49	73.9	0.836	7.04	
All parties	3.86	075.4	0.896	6.45	

In general, the views of the members of the senior management, the faculty and their assistants and the administrative body agreed on the performance criteria as a component of the control systems, and obtained a high approval rate respectively (77.58%, 74.76%, 73.9%).

The researchers attributed this to the keenness of the Council of the Islamic University to excel in its performance because of strong competition from universities in the Gaza Strip and also that the performance standards are clear and flexible to respond to any possible changes.

The researchers also believe that the respondents' response and the high rate of approval of the "performance criteria" questions are due to the belief of the university staff that any other responses may harm the reputation and status of the Islamic University among other universities in the Gaza Strip and abroad.

Analysis of functional performance paragraphs:

The t-test was used for a single sample, and the results are shown in Table (5), which shows the views of the sample of the study sample in the paragraphs of the "functional performance" axis.

Table 5: An analysis of the paragraphs (functional performance)

Organization	Arithmetic mean	Relative weight	standard deviation	T value	Probability Value
Senior management	3.4	70.225	0.864	5.72	0.000
Faculty members and their assistants	3.49	69.69	0.738	8.492	
Members of the administrative board	3.5	69.691	0.601	11.994	
All parties	3.4633	69.86	0.713	8.7353	

In general, the views of the members of "senior management, faculty and their assistants and the administrative body" on the relationship between the dimensions of the control systems in the performance evaluation process in the Islamic University, and obtained a relatively large approval rate, respectively (70.2%, 69.7%, 70%).

Test hypothesis:

There is a significant relationship between the performance criteria and the performance of the job at the Islamic University in the Gaza Strip.

The Pearson test was used to determine the relationship between performance criteria and functional performance at a level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) and the results are shown in Table (6), which shows that the value of the significance level is less than ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) and the calculated value r is greater than the value of tabular r , (0.135), indicating a significant relationship at the level of statistical significance between performance standards and functional performance at the Islamic University of Gaza.

Table 6: correlation coefficient between performance criteria and functional performance

Performance Standards	Functionality					
	Senior management		Faculty members and their assistants		Members of The Administrative Board	
	Coefficient of correlation	Significance	Coefficient of correlation	Significance	Coefficient of correlation	Significance
	73.6	0.000	0.725	0.000	0.72.1	0.000

The r value of the table is at a "free" level of 237 and the level of "0.05" is equal to 0.135

10. CONCLUSIONS

1. The analysis of the results revealed that the performance standards were used at the Islamic University in Gaza at an acceptable level. The relative weight of all the paragraphs was 70.1%, indicating a relationship between performance criteria and performance at the Islamic University in Gaza Strip.
2. The study concluded that there was a moderate agreement among the respondents on performance criteria and performance improvement. The results of the current study with Madi (2011), Shaheen (2007), Saleem (2014), and Hawk (2010) in accordance with standards of performance in achieving regulatory objectives including job performance.
3. The study found that there was a good (medium) approval of the sample on the control systems and their relation to the functional performance (Botora, 2007), (Ben Tarif, 2010), (Jaclyne), (Olorunsola E.O, 2012) and (Kazan, 2013).

11. RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The study recommended working on continuous updating in the performance standards used by the university as required by the nature of the work. It may be necessary to benefit from the technological and information development, which positively affects the employees and improve their performance.
2. It also recommended the follow-up and review of standards of performance and work to modify them in line with the mission of the university and the objectives of the university to reach them. This is done through:
 - Setting clear and understandable performance standards for all university employees.
 - Link incentives and rewards to performance standards
 - Using performance reports at the university to sign up promotions and rewards.
 - Providing incentives and rewards encouraging the recruitment of distinguished human cadres.
 - Work on reviewing and adjusting the standards according to the surrounding changes and if necessary

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